

QSAR modeling of aquatic toxicity of aromatic aldehydes using artificial neural network (ANN) and multiple linear regression (MLR)[†]

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Abstract : In the present work, quantitative structure-activity relationship analysis (QSAR) to predict the toxic potency of 77 aromatic aldehydes to ciliate *Tetrahymena pyriformis* has been investigated by means of multiple linear regression (MLR) and artificial neural network (ANN). The relationships between structure and toxicity were examined quantitatively using octanol/water partition coefficient (log Kow) encoding hydrophobic and molecular connectivity index depicting topological structural features of aldehydes. The data set was split into train and test set and these sets were used to derive statistically robust and predictive (both internally and externally) models. The study demonstrates that both MLR and ANN models have good predictive power but ANN model shows a better statistical parameter in comparison with MLR model.

Keywords : QSAR, ANN modeling, QSTR, structure toxicity relationship, aquatic toxicity, aldehyde toxicity.

1. Introduction

The environment is regularly exposed to new chemical compounds and the toxic burden is increasing every day. These chemicals are mainly generated by agrochemical, petrochemical, and pharmaceutical industries. Due to the risk to human and environmental health from the organic chemicals, there is considerable concern on the toxicity of these compounds^{1,2}. The toxicity data have been documented only for small number of substances and most of the toxicity information available is based on experimental (*in vivo* or *in vitro*) testing. Although this can provide reliable data about toxicity of a given compound with a biological system, it is time consuming and expensive, so it is not suitable for the screening large number of compounds^{3,4}. An alternative to experimental testing is the use of *in silico* methods or computational methods to predict the toxicity⁵. Quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR) has become very at-

tractive and promising tool for theoretical prediction and analysis of toxicity. QSAR method offer higher speed of toxicity screening with lower costs, when compared to experimental testing⁶. It is envisaged that *in silico* methods and QSAR in particular, will play an important role in the reduction of animal testing required for the risk assessment of chemical substances, especially under new legislation such as REACH⁷.

The toxicity of a chemical substance and its intensity can differ widely with the nature of the functional group present in the molecule. The functional group also decides the mechanism of toxic action of the compounds. QSARs are usually developed using compounds of a single chemical class, on the assumption that such a congeneric series has a common functional group hence a common mechanism of action⁸. Mechanistically interpretable QSAR has developed for different class of compounds such as anilines, phenols, esters, aldehydes, ketones, nitro compounds⁹⁻¹³.

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

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Aromatic aldehydes represent one of the important classes of organic compounds and are used as intermediates in the manufacture of pharmaceuticals, flavor and fragrance industry and cosmetics¹⁴. The widespread production and distribution of these compounds in the environment is a serious risk to human and environmental health. Lots of these chemicals were released into environment and accumulate in nearly all environmental compartments, especially in aquatic ecosystems. Information on aquatic toxicity is required in order to assess hazard and risk of chemical substances to marine and freshwater organisms living in the water column¹⁵.

The toxicity or adverse effect of aldehyde is due to mainly by electrophilic reaction with proteins and nucleic acids present in the biological system. Because of their inherent reactivity, these compounds are able to interact with the electron-rich biological macromolecules, in particular proteins and nucleic acids and therefore, have the potential to cause a number of adverse effects and diseases¹⁶.

In the past there are several QSAR studies conducted to model aldehyde toxicity against different aquatic species like, *Tetrahymena pyriformis*, *Poecilia reticulata*, *Vibrio fischeri*, *Pimephales promelas*. In most of the studies aldehydes were included along with compounds having different functional groups¹⁷⁻²⁰. Some studies on aliphatic aldehydes yielded very good QSAR models, but they were based on a small number of homologous compounds or with low predictivity²¹⁻²³.

Netzewa and Schultz developed QSAR models for a set of aromatic aldehydes with MLR using mechanistically interpretable descriptors. The resulting QSAR revealed that the 1-octanol/water partition coefficient (log Kow), and the maximum acceptor superdelocalizability in a molecule (A_{\max}) electrophilicity are descriptor of aldehyde aquatic toxic potency²⁴. Recently QSAR study on the same data set of aldehydes was reported by means of quantum chemical descriptors and ETA descriptors in combination with log Kow^{25,26}.

Agrawal and Khadikar²⁷⁻²⁹ successfully used topological descriptors to model toxicity of many organic compounds. The present study was undertaken to model the aldehyde toxicity using molecular connectivity descriptors depicting topological structural features and

physicochemical descriptor log Kow. In that attempt we used linear regression (MLR) and artificial neural network (ANN) as modeling method.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Toxicity data :

The toxicity values of aldehydes are expressed as log (1/IGC₅₀), the concentrations (mM) producing a 50% growth inhibition on ciliate *Tetrahymena pyriformis* (strain GL-C). The log (1/IGC₅₀) values reported by Natzewa and Schultz²⁴ as mM were used as the dependent variable in QSAR analysis. The data was split into a train set which was used to build the model and test set for prediction.

2.2. Molecular descriptors :

The topological indices used in this study include a large set of connectivity indices³⁰.

A total of 33 molecular connectivity parameters were calculated for each compound. This include connectivity index, average connectivity index, valence connectivity index, average valence connectivity index, solvation connectivity index, modified Randic connectivity, reciprocal distance Randic-type index, reciprocal distance squared Randic-type index. These descriptors represent the topology of the molecules. The octanol/water partition coefficient (log Kow) was taken from the reported values of Natzewa²⁴. An indicator parameter Ip representing 2- and/ or 4-hydroxylated aldehydes are also used. The value of Ip is 1 if it is 2- and/or 4-hydroxylated aldehyde, otherwise zero. All the descriptors were calculated using E-Dragon software and the structures were fully 3D optimized using CORINA before the calculation of the descriptors^{31,32}.

2.3. Model development, validation and performance evaluation :

The main purpose of multiple linear regression (MLR) is to model the relationship between two or more independent variables and a dependent variable by fitting a linear equation to observed data. In the present work, the linear QSAR models were built using MLR method with the variables selected by step wise algorithm. We used SPSS V.10 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) to select the optimum set of descriptors that produces the most significant linear QSAR models from train data set.

The ANN is one of the nonlinear modeling method which is successfully used in many QSAR studies³³. The ANN can incorporate nonlinear relationships between descriptors and activity and often produce superior QSAR models compared to models derived by MLR. In this study we used a three-layered Back-Propagation network (BPANN) which uses supervised learning technique^{34,35}. The network is trained by minimizing the squared error of the network's output, and the error is propagated backwards through the network for adjusting the weights to minimize the error. The neural network simulations were carried out by Weka software³⁶. The architecture of the network consist of three neurons in the input layer, which corresponds to the three descriptors selected in linear model and one neuron in the output layer which is the log (1/IGC₅₀) values. A sigmoid transfer function was used for each neuron in all the three layers. The number of hidden layer neurons, the learning rate and momentum parameter was selected by 10 fold cross validation and the best model giving lowest root mean square error (RMSE) and highest correlation coefficient. Here the train data set (N=62) was randomly divided into 10 groups and the model was trained on 9 groups and the remaining one group is used for testing each time.

The performance of the models was evaluated using the error measures RMSE and calculated using the following formula.

RMSE =

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\log 1/IGC_{50\text{obs}} - \log 1/IGC_{50\text{pred}})^2}$$

where *n* is the number of data points, the parameter log 1/IGC_{50pred} represents the predicted output from the model for a given input log 1/IGC_{50obs}.

Before a QSAR model is used to predict the toxicity of new compounds, it should be validated both internally and externally to ensure that the built model is stable and predictive. In the present study, leave-one-out (LOO) cross-validated R²_{cv} and Predicted residual sum of squares (PRESS) were used to assess the internal predictive ability of the proposed linear models. According to Tropasha^{37,38} rigorous validation through the external validation set is necessary before their practical application or interpretation of the model. To estimate the predictive power of a model, the following set of statistical

criteria are recommended; (i) Correlation coefficient *R* between the predicted and observed activities; (ii) coefficients of determination (predicted versus observed activities *R*₀², and observed versus predicted activities *R*'₀² for regressions through the origin); (iii) slopes *k* and *k*' of regression lines (predicted versus observed activities, and observed versus predicted activities) through the origin. The model has an acceptable predictive power if the following conditions are satisfied;

$$R^2 > 0.6;$$

$$\frac{R^2 - R_0'^2}{R^2} < 0.1 \text{ and } 0.85 \leq K \leq 1.15 \text{ or}$$

$$\frac{R^2 - R_0'^2}{R^2} < 0.1 \text{ and } 0.85 \leq K \leq 1.15$$

$$|R_0'^2 - R_0'^2| < 0.3$$

3. Results and discussion

The QSAR models predictive ability should be tested on an external set of data so the data set was split into train and test set. The entire data was sorted ascending order of log (1/IGC₅₀) values and every fifth compound was selected as test set. Approximately 20% data was selected as test set. The train set of 62 compounds was used for variable selection and model building. Three statistically significant descriptors were selected using the stepwise regression method and this resulted in following regression equations. The log Kow is the most highly correlated descriptor with log (1/IGC₅₀) as observed in eq. (1). Further addition of χ^1A and Ip improved the statistical quality of the models. The linear QSAR model containing three variables give the best results.

$$\log (1/IGC_{50}) = -0.603 + 0.519 (\pm 0.078) \log \text{Kow} \quad (1)$$

N = 62, R = 0.865, R² = 0.748, R²_{Adj} = 0.744, SE = 0.263, F = 178.3, PRESS = 4.166, SSY = 12.377, PRESS/SSY = 0.336, R²_{cv} = 0.664

$$\log (1/IGC_{50}) = 6.624 + 0.423 (\pm 0.071) \log \text{Kow} - 14.836 (\pm 5.009) \chi^1A \quad (2)$$

N = 62, R = 0.918, R² = 0.842, R²_{Adj} = 0.837, SE = 0.210, F = 157.4, PRESS = 2.612, SSY = 13.931, PRESS/SSY = 0.187, R²_{cv} = 0.813

$$\log (1/IGC_{50}) = 4.915 + 0.488 (\pm 0.062) \\ \log \text{Kow} - 11.705 (\pm 4.261) \chi^{1A} \\ + 0.279 (\pm 0.102) \text{Ip} \quad (3)$$

$N = 62$, $R = 0.947$, $R^2 = 0.896$, $R^2_{\text{Adj}} = 0.891$, $\text{SE} = 0.172$, $F = 166.4$, $\text{PRESS} = 1.722$, $\text{SSY} = 14.821$, $\text{PRESS}/\text{SSY} = 0.116$, $R^2_{\text{cv}} = 0.884$

where R is the correlation coefficient, SE is the Standard Error of Estimate. The figures in parentheses with the regression coefficients were standard errors of coefficients.

F is the F -statistics. A reliable MLR model is one that has high R^2 and, low SE values.

The correlation matrix for selected parameters $\log \text{Kow}$, χ^{1A} , Ip is given in Table 2. The correlation matrix shows no inter correlation of selected descriptors. This was further confirmed by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). $VIF = 1/1 - R^2$. In practice, when $VIF > 10$ would indicate multicollinearity among the descriptors³⁹. The VIF value resulting from regressing descriptor $\log \text{Kow}$, χ^{1A} , and Ip are 1.50, 1.375, 1.185 respectively and this further shows that there is no multicollinearity problem for the selected three descriptors.

The adjustable R^2_{Adj} is an important statistical parameter used to explain whether an added variable contributes its fair share in the model. If a variable is added that does not contribute its fair share then R^2_{Adj} will decline. Here we observe that there is an increase in R^2_{Adj} from 0.744 to 0.891 in eq. (3). The improved quality of the eq. (3) as compared with eq. (2) is due to the addition of indicator parameter Ip to the eq. (2).

We have used internal cross-validation method and calculated various cross-validation parameters PRESS (Predicted residual sum of squares), SSY (Sum of squares of the response values), R^2_{cv} (Cross validated correlation coefficient). PRESS is a good estimate of the real predictive power of the model. The value of PRESS is smaller than SSY in all the above equations, so the model predict better than chance. The ratio of PRESS/SSY can be used to calculate approximate confidence intervals of predictions of new observations⁴⁰. To be a reasonable QSAR model, PRESS/SSY should be smaller than 0.4, and eq. (3) has a value 0.116 which indicate excellent model. The developed models are cross-validated by leave-one-out method. The high values observed in case of eq. (3) ($R^2_{\text{cv}} = 0.884$) are indicative of their reliability in prediction of toxicity. We observed that the tri-paramet-

ric linear model (eq. (3)) is the most appropriate for estimating $\log (1/IGC_{50})$. A value of 0.896 for R^2 of this model reveals that it is able to account 89.6% of the variances of the $\log (1/IGC_{50})$.

The selected connectivity descriptor, Average connectivity index chi-1 (χ^{1A}) is an important descriptor, inversely related to molecular branching and complexity³¹.

The χ^{1A} descriptor is calculated using following expression :

Connectivity index χ^1 is defined as

$$\chi^1 = \sum_b (\delta_i \delta_j)^{-1/2}$$

where, b is the number of bonds, the sum runs through all bond in the Hydrogen-depleted molecule, and for each bond $\delta_i \delta_j$ is the product of the vertex degrees of the end atoms i and j . Then the average connectivity is

$$\chi^{1A} = \chi^1/b$$

The predicted values of $\log (1/IGC_{50})$ of the train data set, using this model (eq. (3)) is plotted against experimental values and is shown in Fig. 1. This model gives an R^2 value 0.896 and RMSE 0.1667. The above linear model was used to predict the 15 external test data set which was never used in descriptor selection or model building. The result show an $R^2 = 0.877$ and $\text{RMSE} = 0.190$. The predicted values of $\log (1/IGC_{50})$ of the train and test set using the MLR equation is given in the Table 1.

The architecture of the ANN selected was three neurons in the input layer and two neurons in the hidden layer selected by the auto build function and one output neuron. The same set of descriptors, $\log \text{Kow}$, χ^{1A} and Ip selected by MLR were used as input neurons. A sigmoid transfer function was used in all layers. The ideal value of learning rate η and momentum μ was determined by varying their values from 0.01 to 1.0, the combination of $\eta = 0.054$ and $\mu = 0.20$ which gives the lowest RMSE highest R^2 was selected. To avoid over fitting and overtraining the optimization was done with 10 fold cross validation and 20% of data used for validation. The optimal training end point required was 700 training epochs. With the above selected parameters the number of neurons in the hidden layer was optimized by varying from 1 to 10, the ANN model with 2 hidden neurons gives the best performance. The entire train data

Fig. 1. A plot of observed vs predicted log (1/IGC₅₀) using MLR (eq. (3)) model

Table 1. Observed and predicted values of log (1/IGC₅₀) and selected descriptors

No.	Name	Ip	log Kow	χ^1A	log (1/IGC ₅₀)	pred MLR	pred ANN
1	4-Nitrobenzaldehyde	0	1.56	0.476	0.203	0.106	0.116
2	1-Naphthaldehyde	0	2.67	0.455	0.423	0.893	0.852
3	4-Biphenylcarboxaldehyde	0	3.38	0.46	1.119	1.182	1.232
4	4-Cyanobenzaldehyde	0	1.21	0.486	0.043	-0.182	-0.085
5	Benzaldehyde	0	1.48	0.491	-0.196	-0.109	-0.065
6	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	0	1.99	0.481	-0.057	0.257	0.207
7	4-Fluorobenzaldehyde	0	1.54	0.481	-0.127	0.037	0.057
8	4-Chlorobenzaldehyde	0	2.13	0.481	0.4	0.325	0.261
9	4-Ethylbenzaldehyde	0	2.52	0.486	0.291	0.457	0.372
10	Terephthaldicarboxaldehyde	0	1.36	0.486	-0.086	-0.109	-0.046
11	4-Anisaldehyde	0	1.65	0.486	-0.047	0.032	0.037
12	4-Ethoxybenzaldehyde	0	2.31	0.488	0.073	0.331	0.252
13	4-Acetamidobenzaldehyde	0	1.25	0.477	-0.224	-0.058	0.016
14	2-Chlorobenzaldehyde	0	2.33	0.483	0.487	0.4	0.322
15	3-Chlorobenzaldehyde	0	2.26	0.481	0.406	0.389	0.316
16	2-Nitrobenzaldehyde	0	1.74	0.478	0.167	0.17	0.152
17	3-Nitrobenzaldehyde	0	1.47	0.476	0.178	0.062	0.088
18	3-Anisaldehyde	0	1.71	0.486	0.232	0.062	0.056
19	3-Bromobenzaldehyde	0	2.48	0.481	0.506	0.496	0.417
20	3-Fluorobenzaldehyde	0	1.76	0.481	0.154	0.145	0.126
21	2,4-Dichlorobenzaldehyde	0	3.08	0.474	1.036	0.871	0.85
22	2,4,5-Trimethoxybenzaldehyde	0	1.19	0.483	-0.101	-0.157	-0.06
23	4-(Dimethylamino)benzaldehyde	0	1.81	0.476	0.231	0.228	0.198
24	4-Phenoxybenzaldehyde	0	3.96	0.461	1.257	1.453	1.559
25	2-Fluorobenzaldehyde	0	1.76	0.483	0.079	0.121	0.104
26	4-Butoxybenzaldehyde	0	3.37	0.49	0.716	0.826	0.808

Table-1 (contd.)

27	4-(Pentyloxy)benzaldehyde	0	3.89	0.49	1.179	1.08	1.154
28	Pentafluorobenzaldehyde	0	2.39	0.462	0.815	0.675	0.609
29	2-Chloro-5-nitrobenzaldehyde	0	2.25	0.471	0.527	0.501	0.432
30	2-Chloro-6-fluorobenzaldehyde	0	2.51	0.475	0.155	0.581	0.508
31	3-Cyanobenzaldehyde	0	1.18	0.486	-0.02	-0.197	-0.092
32	2-Chloro-3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde	0	1.72	0.475	0.204	0.195	0.178
33	3-Chloro-2-fluoro-5-(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde	0	3.5	0.454	1.723	1.311	1.38
34	2,3,5-Trichlorobenzaldehyde	0	3.69	0.468	1.499	1.24	1.323
35	2-Fluorencarboxaldehyde	0	3.43	0.434	1.499	1.511	1.56
36	2-Methyl-1-naphthaldehyde	0	3.17	0.452	1.231	1.173	1.201
37	4-Methyl-1-naphthaldehyde	0	3.17	0.452	1.123	1.173	1.201
38	Phenanthrene-9-carboxaldehyde	0	3.84	0.439	1.708	1.652	1.713
39	5-Hydroxy-2-nitrobenzaldehyde	0	1.75	0.471	0.329	0.257	0.231
40	3-Hydroxy-4-nitrobenzaldehyde	0	1.47	0.471	0.273	0.12	0.14
41	3-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	0	1.38	0.481	0.085	-0.041	0.011
42	3,4-Dimethoxy-5-hydroxycarboxaldehyde	0	0.69	0.479	-0.39	-0.355	-0.138
43	2,3-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.03	0.475	0.111	0.137	0.137
44	2,5-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.33	0.474	0.277	0.295	0.342
45	3,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.03	0.474	0.107	0.149	0.15
46	3,4,5-Trihydroxybenzaldehyde	1	0.42	0.468	-0.196	-0.079	-0.15
47	2,3,4-Trihydroxybenzaldehyde	1	0.79	0.469	0.001	0.09	0.063
48	2,4,6-Trihydroxybenzaldehyde	1	0.72	0.468	0.128	0.068	0.031
49	2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.33	0.474	0.515	0.295	0.342
50	3-Ethoxy-2-hydroxycarboxaldehyde	1	2.17	0.483	0.85	0.6	0.701
51	4,6-Dimethoxy-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.86	0.479	0.617	0.496	0.591
52	2-Hydroxy-3-nitrocarboxaldehyde	1	1.84	0.472	0.87	0.568	0.667
53	4-Hydroxy-3-nitrobenzaldehyde	1	1.48	0.471	0.614	0.404	0.475
54	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	1	2.99	0.452	1.32	1.364	1.331
55	5-Bromovanillin	1	1.92	0.474	0.617	0.584	0.684
56	4-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	1	2.62	0.452	1.05	1.183	1.224
57	5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde	1	2.65	0.474	1.009	0.94	0.998
58	2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.81	0.483	0.424	0.425	0.514
59	3-Bromo-4-hydroxycarboxaldehyde	1	2.15	0.474	0.61	0.696	0.797
60	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.21	0.479	-0.03	0.178	0.2
61	3,5-Dibromo-4-hydroxycarboxaldehyde	1	2.77	0.468	0.89	1.069	1.101
62	3-Ethoxy-4-hydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.58	0.481	0.015	0.336	0.405
Test set							
63	4-Bromobenzaldehyde	0	2.48	0.481	0.587	0.496	0.417
64	2-Tolualdehyde	0	2.26	0.483	0.011	0.365	0.291
65	3-Tolualdehyde	0	1.99	0.481	0.081	0.257	0.207
66	Phenyl-1,3-dialdehyde	0	1.36	0.486	0.183	-0.109	-0.046
67	2-Anisaldehyde	0	1.72	0.488	0.148	0.043	0.037
68	2,4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde	0	1.79	0.484	-0.056	0.124	0.103
69	2-Bromobenzaldehyde	0	2.48	0.483	0.477	0.473	0.391
70	4-Isopropylbenzaldehyde	0	2.92	0.476	0.67	0.77	0.724
71	6-Chloro-2-fluoro-3-methylbenzaldehyde	0	3.01	0.469	1.238	0.896	0.875

Table-1 (contd.)

72	3-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde	0	0.97	0.479	-0.142	-0.218	-0.074
73	3-Methoxysalicylaldehyde	1	1.37	0.481	0.377	0.233	0.275
74	3,5-Dibromosalicylaldehyde	1	3.42	0.468	1.648	1.387	1.28
75	2-Chloro-4-hydroxycarboxaldehyde	1	2.28	0.474	0.89	0.76	0.854
76	4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	1	1.35	0.481	0.266	0.223	0.262
77	5-Bromosalicylaldehyde	1	2.8	0.474	1.107	1.013	1.048

is trained in the network with the architecture of 3-2-1, with the optimized parameters, Neural network were able to estimate quite accurately, most of the $\log(1/IGC_{50})$, it gives a R^2 of 0.906 and RMSE 0.16. A plot of the experimental and predicted value of $\log(1/IGC_{50})$ of the train data using the ANN model is plotted in Fig. 2. Using the trained network the test set was used for pre-

the training set. Statistics for the estimation of $\log(1/IGC_{50})$ values in the test set are presented in Table 3. Examination of the results of RMSE and R^2 values in prediction of the independent test set show that ANN model have slightly higher predictive power. Both models show good and acceptable external predictive power and satisfy the following conditions for the external test set the R^2

Fig. 2. A plot of observed vs predicted $\log(1/IGC_{50})$ using ANN model.

diction and gives $R^2 = 0.904$, and RMSE = 0.184. The predicted values of $\log(1/IGC_{50})$ of the train and test data is presented in the Table 1.

Analysis of the training set fit results would suggest that the ANN model will predict $\log(1/IGC_{50})$ values more effectively than MLR model on account of their larger R^2 of 0.906 and smaller RMSE value 0.16. This demonstrates that the performance of non-linear models is better than that of a linear MLR model. However, we can only prove this after conducting rigorous cross validation procedures. The model predictivity was evaluated using a test set of 15 aromatic aldehydes not included in

> 5 , $R^2 - R_0^2/R^2$ or $R^2 - R_0'^2/R^2 = < 0.1$, and K or K' within 0.85-1.15, and $R_0^2 - R_0'^2 < 0.3$.

The comparison of performance of the linear and non-linear models demonstrate that the ANN model predict the $\log(1/IGC_{50})$ better than MLR model. When comparing the results of the model to those of previously published models²⁴⁻²⁶, it showed that the presented model possesses some obvious superiority and the topological descriptor χ^1A are found to be of practically the same statistical quality as those that require quantum mechanical calculations.

Table 2. Inter correlation of selected descriptors

	log (1/IGC ₅₀)	log Kow	χ^1A	Ip
log (1/IGC ₅₀)	1.000	0.865	-0.673	0.032
log Kow	0.865	1.000	-0.465	-0.3
χ^1A	-0.673	-0.465	1.000	-0.087
Ip	0.032	-0.3	-0.087	1.000

Table 3. Predictivity of the external test set (n = 15)

Statistics	MLR	ANN
R ²	0.877	0.904
R ² - R ₀ ² /R ²	0.008	0.015
R ² - R' ₀ ² /R ²	0.000	0.001
$\left R_0^2 - R_0'^2 \right $	0.007	0.012
K	0.84	0.82
K'	1.11	1.15
RMSE	0.190	0.184

5. Conclusion

The risks that chemicals may pose to humans and environment is the current focus of regulatory agencies. QSAR is an alternative to *in vitro* and *in vivo* toxicity testing of chemicals to biological systems. In this work, a new linear and nonlinear QSAR model to predict the toxicity of aromatic aldehydes in *Tetrahymena pyriformis* was established. Three descriptors were chosen as the best by using stepwise regression method and used to build QSRR models for toxicity prediction. Both linear and nonlinear methods seem to be useful, although a comparison of results of two methods revealed the superiority of the nonlinear ANN model. Hydrophobicity, branching of molecule, hydroxyl group at position 2- and/or at position 4 is important factors influencing toxicity of aromatic aldehyde. The proposed methods, due to their high predictive ability and simplicity could be a useful aid to the costly experiments for determining the aquatic toxicity of aromatic aldehydes.

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